

Preparation, Infrared and Electronic Spectra of Some Copper(II) Acetoacetarylamide Complexes

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Copper(II) complexes of acetoacetarylamide have been prepared. The infrared investigations of the complexes of copper(II) indicate the coordination of these ligands to copper through oxygen atom which is indicated by a decrease in the C = O stretching frequencies. The complexes are all paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.68-1.76$ B.M.). A square planar structure is suggested.

THERE have been numerous studies on metal chelates with ligands containing oxygen donors, for instance β -diketones^{1,2}. Recent reports³⁻⁶ were concerned with the isolation of acetoacetanilide chelates of copper(II), beryllium(II), chromium(III), iron(III), aluminium(III), yttrium(III), neodymium(III), praseodymium(III) and samarium(III). Magnetic moment and electronic absorption spectra of some copper(II) complexes⁷ of acetoacetanilide and acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide are also described. The effect of conjugate chelation on carbonyl frequencies has been studied by Shah *et al.*⁸ by comparing the IR and UV spectra of acetoacetarylamides and their corresponding mono-sodio compounds. The present paper describes a systematic study regarding the preparation, magnetic properties, infrared and electronic, spectra of acetoacetarylamide chelates of copper(II).

Materials and Methods

Aceto-acetanilide, acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide, acetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide, acetoacet-*o*-anisidide and acetoacet-*m*-xylylidide used were of AR grade. Copper(II) chloride dihydrate used for the preparation of chelates was a BDH product.

Preparation of the complexes :

The complexes of the general type (CuL₂) were prepared by the following common method.

Solution of CuCl₂.2H₂O (0.01 mole) was prepared in minimum amount of water and that of acetoacetarylamide (0.02 mole) in minimum amount of ethanol. These two solutions were then mixed and the pH adjusted to ~5 using sodium acetate solution. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

Magnetic susceptibility and spectral measurements : The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was determined at room temperature by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were applied using Pascal's constants⁹.

The infrared spectra were recorded in Laxatol mull in the region of 2 to 16 microns on Beckman IR-5 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in the range 350 to 800 nm in chloroform solution were measured on a Beckman DK-2A recording spectrophotometer.

Analyses : Copper in the complexes was estimated by EDTA titration after decomposing them with a mixture of nitric, sulphuric and perchloric acids. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's procedure.

Results and Discussion

The results of analyses and physical properties are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Found (%)		Calc. (%)		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Wave number ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
		Cu	N	Cu	N		
1. [Cu(acet-anil) ₂]	Dark green	15.2	6.34	15.3	6.74	1.76	15040, 17390
2. [Cu(acet- <i>p</i> -tol) ₂]	Dark green	13.9	6.02	14.2	6.33	1.75	15110, 17790
3. [Cu(acet- <i>o</i> -Cl-anil) ₂]	Pale green	13.9	5.65	13.1	5.78	1.68	14810, 16180
4. [Cu(acet- <i>p</i> -Cl-anil) ₂]	Yellowish green	13.3	5.62	13.1	5.78	1.68	16000 (broad)
5. [Cu(acet- <i>o</i> -anis) ₂]	Green	13.4	5.27	13.4	5.89	1.70	14660, 18180
6. [Cu(acet- <i>m</i> -xyli) ₂]	Light green	13.7	5.36	13.5	5.94	1.68	15380, 18180

where acet-anil = acetoacetanilide, acet-*p*-tol = acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, acet-*o*-Cl-anil = acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide, acet-*p*-Cl-anil = acetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide, acet-*o*-anis = acetoacet-*o*-anisidide, and acet-*m*-xyli = acetoacet-*m*-xylylidide.

Magnetic properties: The magnetic moments (Table 1) of the complexes are in the range 1.68–1.76 B.M. These values are close to the 'spin-only' value expected for 3d⁹ copper(II) complexes with normal magnetic properties¹⁰. The present values lend some support for planar or distorted octahedral structures rather than for a tetrahedral geometry.

Electronic spectra: The existence of a planar ligand field results in the presence of three bands which may appear in the form of a very broad asymmetric band near 16,000 cm⁻¹. Square planar complexes of copper(II) are well established¹¹ and give two bands at 15,000 cm⁻¹ and 18,000 cm⁻¹. The electronic spectra of copper(II) bisacetoacetyl- amides consist of two bands in the regions 14,660–16,000 cm⁻¹ and 17,390–18,180 cm⁻¹. These bands are of the type found for planar complexes with four oxygen donors⁷.

Infrared spectra: The relevant infrared spectral bands together with their assignments are given in Table 2. The infrared spectral data of the ligands and their metal chelates throw considerable light on the points of attachment of the ligand to the metal.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA FOR ACETOACETARYLAMIDE (a) AND COPPER(II) COMPLEX, (b) IN CM⁻¹.

NH	C = O Stretching	Amide band			Chelate	Phenyl Vibration	
		I	II	III			
<i>Acetoacetanilide</i>							
(a)	3344	1724	1681	1558	1250	1613	1515
(b)	3413	1587	1634	1558	1236	1587	1515
<i>Acetoacet-p-toluidide</i>							
(a)	3378	1736	1678	1562	1250	1626	1534
(b)	3413	1587	1623	1558	1266	1587	1511
<i>Acetoacet-o-chloroanilide</i>							
(a)	3279	1724	1695	1558	1266	1613	1527
(b)	—	1597	1634	1558	1250	1597	1527
<i>Acetoacet-p-chloroanilide</i>							
(a)	3333	1733	1681	1562	1250	1634	1527
(b)	3401	1610	1639	1560	1266	1600	1504
<i>Acetoacet-o-anisidide</i>							
(a)	3390	1736	1695	1548	1266	1623	1504
(b)	3472	1605	1634	1562	1263	1605	1538
<i>Acetoacet-m-xylidide</i>							
(a)	3333	1736	1681	1550	1274	1613	1522
(b)	3460	1608	1639	1558	1258	1605	1527

Shah *et al.*⁸ studied the IR spectra of free ligands and assigned the strong band appearing in the range 1724–1736 cm⁻¹ to an unconjugated C = O stretching vibration. Appearance of this band as well as the

absence of any –OH stretching vibration indicates that acetoacetyl amides under ordinary condition exist almost in keto form. This is in accordance with IR and NMR spectral study by Sen *et al.*⁵.

In all the copper chelates the carbonyl stretching frequency is lowered from the range 1724–1736 cm⁻¹ (in reagents) to 1587–1610 cm⁻¹ (in chelates). The lowering of the carbonyl frequency in chelates relative to that in reagents shows the decrease in ketonic character of C = O group in chelates. This illustrates that the carbonyl oxygen is taking part in bonding with metal. As the composition of chelates has been established as 1 : 2, four carbonyl oxygens must be acting as donor atoms. The magnetic properties have also indicated the possibility of square planar stereochemistry and hence the following probable structure of these chelates may be assigned from IR study.

The absorption band around 1600 cm⁻¹ is assigned primarily to C = C in the chelate enol form. This confirms the existence of enol form of reagents in equilibrium with keto form.

The strong absorption band obtained at 3279–3390 cm⁻¹ in reagents may be attributed to the intramolecularly bonded N–H stretching vibrations. This N–H stretching frequency is shifted to 3413–3472 cm⁻¹ in chelates. This increase in frequency shows that the hydrogen of NH is free and not intramolecularly bonded. This also confirms that there is no bonding through nitrogen, that is nitrogen does not act as donor in these chelates.

The strong band at 1678–1695 cm⁻¹ in reagents is shifted in metal chelates to 1623–1639 cm⁻¹ and is identified as to the amide I band. The band at 1548–1562 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to amide II band. According to Miyazawa *et al.*¹² the vibration responsible for this absorption is a mixture of N–H bending (~60%) and C–N stretching (~40%). The amide III band (C–N stretching and N–H bending) can be located at 1250–1274 cm⁻¹.

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